

CORRUPTION, INCOME INEQUALITY AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: AN EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT: *The present study attempted to analyze the impact of corruption on output and income inequality in long run and short run using time series data spanning from 1980 to 2013 for Pakistan. After testing stationary properties through Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron (PP) unit root tests, Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) developed by (Pesaran & Shin, 1999) and (Pesaran, Shin, & Smith, 2001) has been applied. Data have been obtained from World development Indicators (WDI), Pakistan's Economic Survey, International Country Risk Guide (ICRG), Deininger and Squire and UNO-WIDER data set. Findings of the study indicate that corruption exerts negative and statistically significant effects on output while positive and statistically significantly effect on income inequality in the long run. In short run, corruption affects output positively and significantly. Impact of corruption on income inequality is also positive but statistically insignificant in short run. Government expenditures positively affect output but the income inequality negatively in Pakistan.*

KEYWORDS: *Corruption, Inequality, Economic Growth, ARDL*

1. INTRODUCTION

Observing the growth rate of developing economies, one wonders to notice that each economy is facing serious hurdles in the way of their development. Although these economies attempt best effort to improve their growth and welfare, but some problems became so rampant that they influence and damage all institutions internally and do not let them grow. Corruption is the main evil among these problems.

Corruption is an ancient universal problem having various degrees with its harmful effects on growth and development of economies. It is considered as the root cause of the entire problems of any economy. Corruption is termed as a harmful infection which assaults the basic structures needed for general public's dynamic working in a society. It is worldwide problem that retards economic growth and reduces the chances of developing. It is a symptom and outcome of institutional deficiency with negative effects on economic growth (Ugur & Dasgupta, 2011).

Economists recognize that institutions play central role in enhancement of economic growth now a days and corruption's presence in any country indicates that its institutions are weak. When institutions are weak, legal system of the country cannot work properly which results in loss of welfare. The economic impact of corruption is controversial. As (Leff, 1964) claimed that corruption greases the wheel of bureaucracy and institutions while (Kaufmann & Wei, 1999) are of the view that it exerts bad influence on institutions. Institution quality in the presence of corruption may be effective in short time period but not in long run.

Corruption is defined as transfer of interest from public to private sector. Corruption is "The misuse of public office for private advantages" (Sandholtz & Gray, 2003). It is every transaction between actors from the private and public sectors through mutual utilities that are illegally converted into private benefits. Transparency International (TI) defined corruption as, "abuse of entrusted political power for personal gain" (Faull, 2007). Corruption exists in various forms like bribery, dishonesty, fraud,

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embezzlement, blackmailing, favoritism, nepotism, extortion and also may be present sector wise as judicial corruption, political corruption, bureaucratic corruption and electoral corruption etc.

As corruption adversely affects the economic and social development of developing as well as developed countries, major institutions started probing the sources and solutions of corruption. World Bank recognized corruption as the main hurdle in way of socio economic development. It deteriorates advancement of economies by weakening their institutional basis and distorting principle of law on which economic growth rest upon. International Monetary Funds (IMF) organization depicts corruption that a large number of the reasons for the violation are economic in nature, thus are its outcomes, poor administration obviously is unfavorable to financial movement and welfare (Akai et al., 2005).

Though International institutions steadily claim that corruption impedes growth of economies by misrepresenting principle of law and weakening their institutional basis, yet Economists are not surely concurred with the case from hypothetical perspective. Economists hold startlingly different views regarding the impact of corruption on growth (Anoruo & Braha, 2005). Different studies show the correlation between corruption and output growth of economies, but with conflicting results.

(Leff, 1964), (Huntington, 1968) and (Lui, 1985) argued that corruption promotes economic growth. They are of the view that corruption is favorable for an economy as it lubricates the wheels of bureaucracy. According to them corruption has the effectiveness to make an economic representative more effective and competent and, it stimulates growth and further development of economies. (Huntington, 1968) and (Leff, 1964) claim that corruption might stimulate economic growth by relaxing the inflexible and ineffective rules levied by government. (Lui, 1985) says that while assigning occupational certificates for business to companies or corporations, bureaucrats give superiority to those who assess time in the most ideal way. According to him corruption has positive impact in short runs by efficiently allocating while the adverse effect on long runs.

A different view is that corruption exerts harmful effects on economic growth. Researchers like (Gould & Amaro-Reyes, 1983), (Mauro, 1997), (Kaufmann, 1997), (Pellegrini & Gerlagh, 2004), and some international organizations like the World Bank, United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and International Monetary Fund (IMF) analyzed that corruption has unfavorable impacts on development and improvement of economies.

In any economy, corruption results from several factors like high poverty, unemployment, political instability, high discretion in formulating and implementing policies, extensive role of bureaucracy, ineffective and slow legal system, low salaries in the public service, lack of economic freedom, price control activities, natural resource endowment and sociological factor and weak governance (Mauro, 1997). All these are sources of rent and contribute to rent seeking behavior. Furthermore, lack of accountability, job opportunities, no transparency in affairs and deal also cause corruption.

The presence of corruption in any economy leads to so many social and economic problems that decrease the economic growth of that country. When corruption exists, investors know that they have to pay bribes for issuance of the authorization, so they perceive corruption as a duty that reduces the incentive to invest which lessens the investment and in turn retards economic growth.

Corruption leads to misallocation of talent. Well and highly educated people indulge in rent seeking activities rather than productive work which discourage growth of economies. In a corrupt system, tax revenue declines because of tax exemption, tax evasion and low tax revenue that creates budget deficit affecting growth adversely. Corruption may also distort government expenditure through inefficient

allocation. This misapplication of government spending leads to lower quality of infrastructure and community services. All these factors that are adversely affected by the corruption result in reduction of economic growth (Mauro, 1997).

Corruption does not affect only economic growth of a country, but also increases unequal distribution of income (Ullah & Ahmad, 2007). Income inequality can be defined as “the uneven distribution of total national income among households”. Low income people are mostly affected by corruption as it diverts public spending from the projects which are beneficial for poor people like education and health to those projects which are favorable for high income group like defense. This in turn leads to increase in income inequality and poor become poorer.

Inequality is generally viewed as unfair because it is adversely related to social welfare through different ways. As inequality leads to economic inefficiency in the sense that people cannot borrow money and usually cannot properly educate their children and start or expand their business. Due to high income disparity general saving rate in the economy declines and capital flight starts which lead to inefficient allocation of resources or assets. Inequality also results in social instability by strengthening the political power of the rich and facilitating rent seeking behavior. All these aspects tend to lower both per capita income and rate of GDP growth in the economies which in turn deteriorates social welfare.

The main aspects that increase unequal distribution of income includes asset distribution, distribution of income among factors of production, transfers from households, government, tax and spending structure of the govt. It may also increase due to increase in corruption. According to literature there exists significant and positive relationship between income disparity and corruption (Ullah & Ahmad, 2007).

Corruption encourages inequality through different ways. Firstly, it lowers development of economies by misallocating the resources. Secondly, it constructs a biased tax system that consists of tax exemption, tax evasion, poor management and taxation system favorable to well-connected person. Thirdly, by diverting funds allocated for poor targeting program to the personal benefits (Gupta, Davoodi, & Alonso-Terme, 2002).

Asset ownership also raises income inequality, economies where assets are concentrated to a small elite group their owner use different means to make policies favorable for them due to the corrupt system (Gupta et al., 2002). Income inequality accelerates also by creating an inducement of more investment in those projects in which capital is used and lower investment in the projects in which labor is employed. Such biases in investment deprive poor income creating opportunities.

Corruption also affects inequality through human capital by diverting public spending toward higher education and health facilities that are accessible for high income group only (Mauro, 1997). These are some of the factors through which corruption enhances unequal distribution of income and that further lead to other social and economic problems and affect economic growth as well as development.

2. PROFILE OF PAKISTAN

Pakistan is a developing country having 179.2 million population and is facing the several social and economic problems for the last few decades. These evils have stunted the speed of economic progress and development. As the growth rate of Pakistan is very low and volatile. Despite of different problems, fiscal year 2013-14 shows improvement in the growth of the economy in different sectors with 4.14% growth rate in fiscal year 2013-14 being higher than the 3.6% growth rate for fiscal year 2012-13.

Pakistan's economy has to face various problems like poverty, illiteracy, energy crises, corruption and

political instability, international interferences, terrorism, overpopulation, economic crises, health issues and lack of law enforcement which hinder foreign and domestic investment and growth also. Corruption is also a major problem of our economy and is everywhere since a long period of time. Almost all the institutions, including educational institutions are directly or indirectly involved in corruption. Unfair means are used in every field of life. It is too difficult to get one's rights without bribery.¹The resources needed to facilitate needful are wasted due to corruption. Sometime, even development projects remain incomplete owing to corruption.

According to Transparency International (TI), Pakistan counted 127 out of 175 countries on the basis of the CPI (TI, 2013). This shows the enhancement in country's ranking on the index basis during last 5 years. As the country 'score was 139 from 180 in 2009, 143 from 178 in 2010, 134 from 182 in 2011 and 139 from 174 countries in 2012. In 2013 it is 127 out of 175 countries it seems that corruption decreased in Pakistan our last five years, which is a positive sign for the country (TI, 2013).

Figure 1 shows corruption trend in Pakistan over the last few years. It illustrates the fluctuations in CPI of Pakistan. In 2002 corruption decreased as compared to 2001 and it rose till 2005 due to poor governance as according to the Global Competitiveness Report poor quality governance and corrupt behavior of bureaucrats is the main obstacle to foreign investment in Pakistan. After that there was a decline in corruption till 2008. Yet again, there was rising trend in corruption from 2008 to 2010. After 2010 there is declining trend in corruption till 2013. This fall in corruption is result of the effective working of National Accountability Bureau (NAB) an anti-corruption agency of Pakistan. Although there is a decline in corruption for last 4 year yet it is very high as Pakistan is 27th corrupt country (TI, 2013).

Figure 1 Corruption Trend in Pakistan

Although Pakistan has observed progress in the world CPI index in 2013 from 27th to 28th and ranks from 139 to 127 from 177 countries, which is a good indication for the country. However, Statistics of SAARC countries show that in Pakistan corruption is higher than almost all other SAARC member countries except Bangladesh. Data for Maldives was not available (TI, 2013). SAARC countries include Pakistan, Bangladesh, India, Sri Lanka, Bhutan, Nepal and Maldives.

Still, it is utmost need to reforms accountability and anti-corruption strategies in all departments and institutions in Pakistan to reduce corruption.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corruption_in_Pakistan

Figure 2 Corruption in SAARC Countries

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretically, there are different views regarding relationship between corruption and economic growth. Most common among those are theory of rent seekers, theory of bribe and the relationship of growth, efficiency and corruption. The theory of rent-seekers was proposed by (Krueger, 1974), (Tullock, 2003) and (Bhagwati, 1982). According to them, economic representatives have a basic inspiration of rent-seeking and they try to obtain the highest rent, or income, possible within or without the rules of economic and social conduct. The theory of bribe was presented by (Rose-Ackerman, 1978) in "Political Economy of Bribe". In this view, corruption is associated with market imperfections. Last view was presented by (Murphy, Shleifer, & Vishny, 1993). The main concern of this view is the correlation amongst institutions, corruption and economic development.

Empirically, there are various views of economist regarding effect of corruption on economic growth and income inequality as well. As (Ahmad, Ullah, & Arfeen, 2012) analyzed the link between corruption and output growth using growth model on the basis of theoretical framework. GMM (Generalized method of moment) technique was applied to estimate the relationship using data set from 1984 to 2009 of 71 developed and developing economies. International country risk guide (ICRG) data set were used for corruption. Outcomes of the study indicated the presence of inverse u shaped relationship between corruption and growth.

(Ugur & Dasgupta, 2011) conducted meta-analysis of countries to analyze link between corruption and economic growth using panel data of almost seventy two countries and applying fixed effect and random effect method. Findings of the study affirmed that corruption exerts negative impact on economic growth directly as well as indirectly and effect is strong in low income countries.

(Dincer & Gunalp, 2012) explored the impact of corruption on inequality and poverty using different measures of both inequality and poverty like Atkinson indexes, Gini index and Standard deviation of the logarithms etc. Panel data set of fifty US states over the period 1981-97 was used. Corruption was measured by number of people indulged in the crime instead of indices. The set of control variables was also included in the analysis and OLS estimation technique was used for estimation. Results illustrated that corruption co-efficient is positive indicating that there exist direct relationship between corruption and inequality and also between corruption and poverty.

(Ullah & Ahmad, 2007) conducted a research study to examine the link of corruption and income inequality using panel data set of 71 developing as well as developed countries from 1986-2006 by

applying GMM estimation technique. Gini coefficient was used to measure inequality while corruption was measured by ICRG index. Trade to GDP ratio, population growth, GDP per worker, Secondary school enrollment, Government expenditure and capital stock per worker are independent variables used in the study. Data used in the study were taken from different sources like IMF, IFS, ICRG and WDI etc. Outcomes of the study showed that there exists significant and positive link between corruption and inequality as higher corruption leads to high inequality in an economy which in turn affects economic growth. The analysis also indicated that Openness and GDP per worker are insignificant while Secondary school enrollment, Government expenditure and population growth have significant effect on income inequality. As higher population growth increases inequality while an increase in secondary school enrollment and Government expenditure have an adverse effect on inequality.

(Akai et al., 2005) used survey data collected from different states of US to evaluate the effect of corruption on economic development for three different time periods short, middle and long run. The 2SLS method was used for estimating results. Findings indicated that in middle and long time period, corruption has significant and adverse effect on output growth while in short run the results are insignificant.

(Mo, 2001) conducted a study to explore the impact of corruption on output growth using a panel data set from 1970 to 1985. OLS method is used to evaluate the effect of corruption on output. The effect has also been checked through transmission channels like investment channel, human capital channel and political instability channel. Variables used in the study are GDP growth, corruption, political rights, human capital and population growth, etc. Results show that corruption affects growth negatively as one percent increase in corruption leads to 0.72% reduction in economic growth. Political instability is strongest channel among all as corruption has positive effect on it while negative effect on others which are investment and human capital.

(Li, Xu, & Zou, 2000) evaluated the relationship of corruption, income inequality and GDP growth using panel data set of different countries for 1980-1992 applying OLS and 2SLS method. Gini coefficient is used for income inequality and ICRG index for corruption. Results suggest that corruption affects economic growth negatively and income inequality in u-shaped.

(Gupta et al., 2002) attempted to explore the effect of corruption on unequal income distribution and poverty. Panel data set over the period of 1980-1997 is used and OLS method is applied. The results indicate that high corruption increases income inequality. Similarly, corruption leads to increase poverty also. Findings confirm that corruption gives rise to both income inequality and poverty by affecting growth, asset distribution, government spending, bias tax system and inadequate access of schooling. The study suggests that effect of corruption can be reduced through good administration and by reducing inequality in distribution of assets and access of educational institution and also by efficient allocation of government expenditures. All these results in decreasing poverty as well as income inequality.

(Mauro, 1998) examined the impact of corruption on different components of government expenditure using panel data set based on simple regression technique and instrumental variable method using ICRG data set for corruption. The component of government expenditure include expenditure on education, transfer, security system, defense, welfare and government consumption spending for almost 100 countries while health expenditures are available only for 30 to 60 countries. The outcomes of this study illustrate that corruption exerts adverse impact on education and health expenditure by diverting them to unproductive activities while positive on all other components.

(Mauro, 1997) conducted a study with two main goals. Firstly, he identified the causes and outcomes of corruption. Secondly, he estimated the corruption's impact on growth, investment and government expenditure using ICRG data set for corruption and applying OLS regression methods. Results show that corruption influences negatively both investment as well as growth. Similarly, corruption discourages government consumption also.

(Egunjobi, 2013) conducted a research study to evaluate the relationship of corruption and economic growth using time series data for 1980-2009 in Nigeria and applied OLS regression technique after checking stationary properties of variables through the ADF unit root test. Further, Causality and impulse response function are also analyzed. Results indicate that corruption exerts adverse impact on economic progress directly. Indirectly, corruption hurts economic growth through affecting foreign direct investment, government expenditure on capital and education negatively. Results of Granger Causality show the existence of unidirectional causality running from economic growth to corruption. Overall study illustrates that corruption affects economic progress negatively directly and also through different channels.

(Pulok, 2010) used an extended version of Solow growth model to analyze the link between corruption and growth using time series data from 1984-2010 in Bangladesh. ARDL estimation approach has been used. First of all, ADF and PP unit root test has been applied on all series to test stationary properties which suggest that ARDL is suitable technique for estimation. ICRG data set is used for corruption and data for other countries have been taken from WDI indicators. Findings of the study investigate that corruption exerts adverse effect on economic progress in the long run for Bangladesh.

(Aliyu & Elijah, 2008) used Barro type endogenous growth model to analyze the effect of corruption on economic progress in Nigeria using time series data from 1986-2007. They also explored the influence of corruption on human capital, physical capital and labour. Initially, some unit root tests were applied to check stationary properties which show that all variables are integrated of orders one. Then Engel Granger co-integration test is used for long run relationship indicates the existence of long run relationship among all variables. In the last Parsimonious Error Correction Model is employed separately to check the effect of corruption on all variables. Findings suggest the existence of negative and significant association among corruption and growth, human capital and labour respectively while positive relationship is found between corruption and physical capital. So corruption exerts negative influence on growth directly and indirectly, and also on human capital and labour while positive effect on physical capital.

(Farooq, Shahbaz, Arouri, & Teulon, 2013) conducted a study to inspect the impact of corruption on economic progress in Pakistan by including financial development using ARDL bound testing approach and Granger causality test. Time series data of GDP, financial development(FD) and TO from 1987 to 2009 were taken from WDI and Pakistan Economic survey and CPI data set published by Transparency International was used for corruption. Results indicate that corruption hinders economic progress and development in the long run in Pakistan while TO and financial development boost the growth. The consequences of Granger causality indicate that there exists bidirectional causality between corruption and growth, trade openness and growth and trade openness and corruption also while unidirectional causality runs from economic growth to financial development.

(Amin, Ahmed, & Zaman, 2013) explored the association between corruption and economic growth for Pakistan over the period of 1985-2010. After testing stationary properties of all series using Augmented Dikey Fuller (ADF) and Philips Perron (PP) unit root test OLS regression method is used. Data used in the study was taken from Pakistan Economic Survey, WDI and Transparency International. Results

indicate that corruption is harmful for economic growth because it adversely affects economic progress in Pakistan.

(Mehmood & Sadiq, 2010) analyzed the link between poverty and government spending using time series data from 1976-2010 applying Johnson cointegration technique. Results of the study indicated the existence of negative relationship between poverty and government expenditure.

(Jamal, 2006) examined the relationship between poverty, inequality and economic progress and use annual data from 1979 to 2006 and also estimated determinants of poverty and inequality by applying OLS and TSLS estimation method and through extrapolating data for poverty and inequality. Results indicate positive correlation between poverty and inequality. Findings also show that inflation, TOT and wage increases inequality while development spending, investment and progressive tax system lead to reduction in inequality

4. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

The emphasis of this study is to evaluate the impact of corruption on Gross domestic product and Income inequality using ARDL bound testing approach. Annual time series data has been used from 1984-2013. Relevant data for the GDP, government expenditure and inflation were taken from World Development Indicator (WDI) and Pakistan Economic Survey (various issues). Data for corruption were taken from international research dataset ICRG. (Deininger & Squire, 1996) and the UN-WIDER Datasets were used for Income Inequality.

4.1 Model Specification

To achieve these objectives models specified are as follow.

Corruption and Economic Growth

To observe the impact of corruption on gross domestic product (GDP) following model was used

$$(1) \quad GDP = f(CORR, GX, INF)$$

Transforming the above function into econometric model

$$(2) \quad \ln GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln CORR_t + \beta_2 \ln GX_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where

LnGDP = Log of GDP

LnCORR = Log of Corruption

LnGX = Log of Government final consumption expenditure

INF = Inflation deflator

ε_t = Error Term

Corruption and Income Inequality

In order to evaluate the effect of corruption on income inequality following model is estimated.

$$(3) \quad GINI = f(CORR, GX, INF)$$

Transforming this function into econometric model

$$(4) \quad GINI_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln CORR_t + \beta_2 \ln GX_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where

GINI = Gini Coefficient as proxy of income inequality

LnCORR = Log of Corruption

LnGX = Log of Government final consumption expenditure

INF = Inflation deflator

ε_t = Error Term

4.2 Methodology

After testing stationary properties of models using ADF and PP unit root test, the present study employed Auto Regressive Distributive Lags (ARDL) estimation method. ARDL is modern and latest technique advanced by (Pesaran & Shin, 1999) and (Pesaran et al., 2001) to achieve the objectives as this technique has several advantages over the previous techniques. Particularly, it can be used for the small sample size while other techniques are only suitable for large sample size (Narayan, 2005). Another advantage of using ARDL is that it can be used whether series are integrated of order one, order zero or mix order of integration.

In ARDL method, constancy of coefficients can be examined using Cumulative sum of Recursive Residual (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of square of Recursive Residual (CUSUMSQ) method which make outcomes more strong. It also has the advantage that long and short run coefficient can be assessed and by using optimal lag for each variable. Moreover Error correction term (ECM) combines short run and long run dynamics in a single equation. ARDL method comprises of three stages. First of all, Error correction Model (ECM) version of Auto Regressive Distributive Lag is estimated using Ordinary Least Square method. General form of both models corruption and economic growth and corruption and income inequality are given below respectively:

$$(5) \quad D\text{LnGDP}_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^a \alpha_1 \Delta \text{LnGDP}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^b \alpha_2 \Delta \text{LnCORR}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^c \alpha_3 \Delta \text{LnGX}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^d \alpha_4 \Delta \text{INF}_{t-i} + \beta_1 \text{LnGDP}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \text{LnCORR}_{t-1} + \beta_3 \text{LnGX}_{t-1} + \beta_4 \text{LnINF}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$(6) \quad D\text{GINI}_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^a \alpha_1 \Delta \text{GINI}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^b \alpha_2 \Delta \text{LnCORR}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^c \alpha_3 \Delta \text{LnGX}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^d \alpha_4 \Delta \text{INF}_{t-i} + \beta_1 \text{GINI}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \text{LnCORR}_{t-1} + \beta_3 \text{LnGX}_{t-1} + \beta_4 \text{INF}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Null and alternative hypothesis of bound test are shown as:

$$H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = 0$$

$$H_1 : \beta_1 \neq 0, \beta_2 \neq 0, \beta_3 \neq 0, \beta_4 \neq 0$$

There are three possible outcomes regarding bound test.

1. F-stat > upper bound (Cointegration)
2. F-stat < lower bound (no Cointegration)
3. F-stat lies between upper and lower bounds (Inconclusive)

If bound test indicate that there exists long run co-integration among the series, next stage is to estimate long run coefficients through long run ARDL model. Before that lag length of variables is selected, either on the basis of AIC or SBC. The present study used AIC to select lag length. Long run models of the study are as given:

$$(7) \quad \text{LnGDP}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \sum_{i=1}^a \text{LnGDP}_{t-i} + \beta_2 \sum_{i=0}^b \text{LnCORR}_{t-i} + \beta_3 \sum_{i=0}^c \text{LnGX}_{t-i} + \beta_4 \sum_{i=0}^d \text{INF}_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$(8) \quad GINI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \sum_{i=1}^a GINI_{t-i} + \beta_2 \sum_{i=0}^b LnCORR_{t-i} + \beta_3 \sum_{i=0}^c LnGX_{t-i} + \beta_4 \sum_{i=0}^d INF_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

After estimating long run coefficients, next stage is to evaluate short run coefficients and ECM for the specific models which show convergence toward equilibrium. To estimate short run results of coefficients, following respective ECM models are used.

$$(9) \quad \Delta LnGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \eta_0(ECM_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a \alpha_1 LnGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^b \alpha_2 \Delta LnCORR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^c \alpha_3 \Delta LnGX_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^d \alpha_4 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \nu_t$$

$$(10) \quad \Delta GINI_t = \alpha_0 + \eta_0(ECM_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^a \alpha_1 GINI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^b \alpha_2 \Delta LnCORR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^c \alpha_3 \Delta LnGX_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^d \alpha_4 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \nu_t$$

In last, diagnostic test used to test the fitness and models. Further stability test applied for testing stability of parameters of both the models over time

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In present study first of all stationary of variables has been checked by using ADF and PP tests developed by (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) and (Phillips & Perron, 1988) respectively in order to avoid spurious results. The results of ADF and PP test of all variables are presented in the table 1.

Table 1 Results of ADF and PP test

Variables	ADF Test		PP Test		Conclusion
	ADF Level	ADF Difference	PP level	PP Difference	
LNGDP	-1.98	-3.49**	-1.60	-3.43**	I(1)
LNCORR	-2.57	-4.88*	-3.18	-5.37*	I(1)
LNGX	-0.98	-4.57*	-1.20	-4.58*	I(1)
GINI	-3.55*	-8.13*	-3.50**	-10.48*	I(0)
INF	-5.48*	-6.59*	-5.48*	-12.18*	I(0)

Note. *show significant at 1%, **show significant at 5% and *** show significant at 10%. The critical values of ADF test at 1, 5 and 10% are -4.227, -3.536 and -3.20 respectively.

The results of ADF and PP test show that GDP, CORR and GX are integrated of order one I(1), these variables are stationary at first difference while GINI and INF are integrated of order zero I(0) i.e., they are stationary at level. Both test results indicate that variables have mixed order of integration. When series have mixed order of integration the suitable technique for long run and short run analysis is ARDL bound testing approach. So the next step is to apply ARDL. In ARDL approach initial stage is to check the presence of long run co integration among the used variables through bound test F-statistic. Lag length is selected on the basis of AIC. Due to small sample size maximum 2 period lag is selected.

Corruption and Economic Growth

In first model, the impact of corruption on gross domestic product is estimated using ARDL bound testing method. First step is to test the existence of co integration among variables. Bound test shows

the existence of long run co-integration among variables.

Table 2 Bound Test Results

Variables	F-Statistic	Critical Values		Lag	Conclusion
		I(0)	I(1)		
F(LGDP/LCORR, LGX, INF)	4.81***[0.01]	3.48	4.46	2	Cointegration

Note. AIC test employed for the selection of lag. * designates that the stat lies below the lower bound, ** designates that it lies between lower and upper bounds and *** designates that it is above the upper bound at five percent significance level.

Result shows that F-Statistics is 4.81 which is higher than upper bound critical value indicating the existence of Cointegration. After the checking the existence of co-integration among variables, next stage is to evaluate long run and short run results of co-efficient using ARDL approach.

Table 3 Long Run Coefficients using the ARDL Approach

ARDL (2,2,0,0) Dependent variable is LNGDP			
Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-Ratio [Prob]
LNCORR	-0.44	0.15	-2.96* [0.008]
LNGX	0.40	0.06	7.09* [0.000]
INF	-0.00	0.00	-0.14 [0.890]
CONSTANT	-3.32	1.42	-2.34**[0.031]

Note. *, ** and *** indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% level accordingly.

Table 3 shows long run results of the effect of corruption on economic growth in Pakistan. Results illustrates that corruption affects GDP negatively in the sense that coefficient is significant at one percent and negatively related to economic progress as it retards economic progress and enhancement. The coefficient of corruption indicates that in the long run, the one percent rise in corruption leads to - 0.44% decreases in economic growth of Pakistan. The results are inconsistent with findings of (Aliyu & Elijah, 2008) and (Farooq et al., 2013). On the basis of the outcomes it can be said that GDP per capita in Pakistan would be 1870.73 US\$ instead of 1299.12 US\$ in 2013 if there is reduction in corruption index by one percent. The coefficient of government expenditure is also significant at one percent and positively associated with Gross domestic products. The coefficient shows that one percent increase in government spending raises the GDP of Pakistan by .40 percent. Coefficient of inflation is insignificant with negative sign, which is indicating the negative impact on GDP.

Table 4 Error Correction Model Representation for selected ARDL Model

ARDL Dependent Variable LNGDP			
Variables	Coefficients	Standard error	t-Ratio [Prob]
DLNGDP	0.25	0.17	1.50 [0.150]
DLNCORR	-0.13	0.09	-1.46 [0.161]
DLNCORR1	0.22	0.09	2.34** [0.030]
DLNGX	0.28	0.07	3.77* [0.001]
DINF	-0.00	0.00	-0.14 [0.889]
CONSTANT	-2.29	1.25	-1.84***[0.081]

ECM(-1)	-0.69	0.17	-4.18* [0.001]
R-Squared=0.73 F(7,19)=6.89[0.00] Durbin-h = -1.16		Adjusted R-Squared=0.61 DW-statistics=2.22	

Note. *, ** and *** indicate significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% level accordingly.

In short run all variables signs and coefficients are according to the theory except corruption. Results of corruption are very interesting in short run as corruption coefficient with two lags and difference indicate that it exerts positive impact on GDP. As coefficient illustrate that one percent rises in corruption leads to 0.22% escalation in GDP of Pakistan. This positive relationship between corruption and growth may be due to the reason that in the short run corruption lubricates the wheel of bureaucracy and other institutions and also makes economic agents and officers more efficient through rent seeking. That's why they work efficiently in short run that accelerate GDP of the economy for the time being.

The estimated ECM is significant at one percent with negative sign which indicate convergence toward equilibrium. ECM coefficient is -0.69 which shows that 69% previous year imbalance or shock is corrected in current year.

In this model R-Squared is 0.73 which indicate that seventy three percent variations in GDP is explained by explanatory variables. F-statistic demonstrates overall significance of the model. Its value is 6.89 which is highly significant. Value of D.W test is 2.22 and Durbin-h test is -1.16 showing no auto correlation.

Table 5 Diagnostics Test Results

Test Statistics	LM Version	F-Statistics [Prob]
Auto Correlation	1.31[.252]	0.87 [.375]
Functional Form	0.05[.836]	0.03 [.864]
Normality	1.30[.523]	Not applicable
Heteroscedasticity	0.24[.626]	0.22 [.642]

Table 5 represents the diagnostic tests of the model which show goodness of fit of the model and there is no problem of serial correlation, Heteroscedasticity, normality and functional form in model. So the model is good fit and correctly specified.

Stability test CUSUM and CUSUMSQ also applied to test the consistency of parameters over time used in the study. The null hypothesis for both the test is that parameters are consistent over time if the statistics of both test lie between the critical bounds at five percent. Figures of both test are shown below indicate that statistics lie between critical bounds so null hypothesis is accepted and parameters of the model are stable and consistent.

Figure 3 CUSUM of Corruption and Economic Growth Model

Figure 4 CUSUMSQ of Corruption and Economic Growth Model

Granger Causality Test Results

Granger causality test has also applied to test the direction of causal link between the variables. The relationship between corruption and income inequality is tested using pair wise causality test. The results are given in table.

Table 6 Pairwise Granger Causality Tests Results

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistics	Prob.
GDP does not Granger Cause CORR	28	2.82	0.080
CORR does not Granger Cause GDP		0.27	0.768

Results of causality test indicated that there exist unidirectional causal relation between output and corruption running from output to corruption and nor the other way round. Results are in line with (Egunjobi, 2013).

5.3 Corruption and Income Inequality

In the present study corruption and income inequality model is also estimated to evaluate the impact of corruption on income inequality. ARDL bound testing approach is applied in which first step is to check presence of Cointegration among variables of interest. Bounds test results are presented in table.

Table 7 Bound Test Results

Variables	F-Statistic	Critical Values		Lag	Conclusion
		I(0)	I(1)		
F(GINI/LCORR,LGX, INF)	4.83***[0.012]	3.48	4.46	2	Cointegration

Note. AIC test employed for the selection of lag. * designates that the stat lies below the lower bound, ** designates that it lies between lower and upper bounds and *** designates that it is above the upper bound at five percent significance level.

Bound test results show that F-Statistic is 4.83 which is higher than upper bound critical value indicating the existence Cointegration among variables. After checking the existence of Co-integration among variables, next stage is to examine long run and short run results using ARDL bound test method.

Table 8 Long Run Coefficients using the ARDL Approach

ARDL(2,1,0,0) Dependent Variable is GINI			
Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-Ratio [Prob]
LNCORR	0.60	0.22	2.75**[0.013]
LNGX	-0.21	0.08	-2.69**[0.015]
INF	-0.04	0.04	-1.01 [0.335]
CONSTANT	4.81	2.09	2.31** [0.033]

Note. *, ** and *** indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% level accordingly.

Table 8 illustrates long run results of second model. Results explain that corruption coefficient is significant at one percent level and sign is positive according to theoretical assertion. The coefficient indicates that one percent rise in corruption will increase income inequality by .60 percent. Empirical literature also shows the direct and significant association between corruption and income inequality. Results are in line with (Gupta et al., 2002), (Dincer & Gunalp, 2012) and (Gyimah-Brempong, 2002) and also according to prior expectation. However, the difference is of magnitude that is due to the fact that these studies are for panel data se while the present study is about time series analysis.

The impact of Government expenditure is adverse and significant indicating that one percent increase in government expenditure decreases the income inequality by 0.21 percent. The coefficient of inflation is insignificant with negative sign.

Table 9 ECM Representation for selected ARDL Model

ARDL(2,1,0,0) Dependent Variable is GINI			
Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-Ratio [Prob]
DGINI	-0.28	0.16	-1.75***[0.096]
DCORR	-0.22	0.31	-.689 [0.500]
DGX	-0.20	0.09	-2.30** [0.032]
DINF	-0.04	0.04	-1.05 [0.304]
CONSTANT	4.66	2.47	1.89*** [0.074]
ECM	-0.97	0.23	-4.14* [0.001]

R-Squared = 0.68	Adjusted R-Squared = 0.56
F(7, 19) = 5.64[0.00]	DW-statistic = 2.06
Durbin-h Test = 0.26	

Table 9 shows short run results and error correction model representation. In short run, corruption affects income inequality negatively but insignificantly and all other variables are according to theory and empirical reviews. ECM in the present model is statistically significant with negative sign showing convergence toward equilibrium. As value of ECM is -0.96 which indicates that 96% disequilibrium from previous year to current year is corrected.

R-squared of this model is .68 showing that 68% variation in dependent variable is explained by explanatory variables. The overall significance of whole model is estimated by F-statistic which is 5.6 and highly significant. DW statistic is 2.05 and Durbin h test statistic is 0.260 which designate that there is no serial correlation in the model.

Table 10 Diagnostics Test Results

Test Statistics	LM Statistics	F-Statistics [Prob]
Auto Correlation	1.31[0.252]	0.87 [0.365]
Functional Form	0.70[0.406]	0.48 [0.501]
Normality	0.12[0.943]	Not applicable
Heteroscedasticity	0.24[0.626]	0.22 [0.642]

Table 10 designates diagnostic test of the recent model which are used to test goodness of fit or model. Results show that in this model, no problem of serial correlation, heteroscedasticity, functional form and normality is there. So the model is good fit.

Stability test is applied to test consistency of parameters over time. The null hypothesis of both test of stability CUSUM and CUSUMSQ test is that parameters are consistent over time if the statistics of both test lie between the critical bounds at five percent. Figures of both the test indicate that statistics lie between critical bound so null hypothesis is accepted and parameters of the model are stable and consistent.

Figure 5 CUSUM of Corruption and Income Inequality Model

Figure 6 CUSUMSQ of Corruption and Income Inequality Model

Granger Causality Test Results

The relationship between corruption and income inequality has also been tested using pair wise causality test. The results are given in following table 11.

Table 11 Pairwise Granger Causality Tests Results

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistics	Prob.
GINI does not Granger Cause CORR	28	4.22	0.050
CORR does not Granger Cause GINI		5.21	0.031

Table 11 shows outcomes of causality test. Results designated that null hypothesis of no causality is rejected and there exists bidirectional causality between inequality and corruption.

6. CONCLUSION AND POLICY SUGGESTIONS

Corruption is threat to economic growth everywhere as it impedes the growth. It interrupts the basic functions of an economy that are allocation, stabilization and distribution and affects them adversely. These functions reduce not only economic growth but also increase income inequality. The present study reveals importance of corruption in discouraging economic progress and enhancement and determining income inequality.

The objective of recent study is to explore impact of corruption on gross domestic product and income inequality in Pakistan using annual data from 1984 to 2013. ARDL estimation technique is applied after testing stationary properties of variables used. Moreover, consistency of parameters is also tested using CUSUM and CUSUMSQ test in ARDL.

The main concern of the study is to examine corruption's impacts. First of all, study analyzes the impact of corruption on GDP of Pakistan. Results show that corruption exerts significant adverse impact on GDP of Pakistan in the sense that one percent rise in corruption decreases GDP by 0.44 percent. These results are according to the prior expectation and empirical findings of (Farooq et al., 2013) and (Amin et al., 2013) for Pakistan, (Pulok, 2010) for Bangladesh, (Aliyu & Elijah, 2008) and (Egunjobi, 2013) for Nigeria. Government expenditure shows positive impact on GDP. One percent rise in government consumption expenditure increases GDP by 0.40 percent.

The study also examines the effect of corruption on income inequality. Findings indicate that corruption

has significant and positive effect on income inequality. When corruption rises by one percent it will increase income inequality by 0.60 percent. Empirical literature also shows the positive and significant relation between corruption and income inequality as highly corrupt countries have high income inequality. Findings are consistent with (Gupta et al., 2002), (Dincer & Gunalp, 2012) and (Gyimah-Brempong, 2002) and also according to expectation. Government expenditure shows negative impact on income inequality that a one percent increase in government consumption expenditure decreases income inequality by 0.21 percent.

The study concludes that corruption is harmful for both gross domestic product and income inequality in the sense that it slows down gross domestic product while augment income inequality. Therefore, some policies should be devised to control it, as the policies which will decrease corruption in the economy will not only promote growth but also result in decreasing income inequality.

One of the main restrictions of present study is the unavailability of data for long time period. Due to this reason short time span is used to explore the effect of corruption on growth and inequality. Moreover, some other important determinants of GDP and income inequality could not be included in the present study due to data limitation. Anyhow, these limitations cannot deny the results of present study that corruption hinders GDP and enhance income inequality for Pakistan.

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